

INNOVATIVE PROCESSING OF METAL AND CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES BY REACTIVE INFILTRATION

M.Kobashi and N.Kanetake

*Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering, Nagoya University
1 Furo-cho, Chikusa-ku, Nagoya, 464-8603, Japan*

SUMMARY: Reactive infiltration technique is an attractive process for the fabrication of metal matrix composites because no special equipment is required to fabricate large scale component. In this process, good wettability between the ceramic and the molten metal is very important. Since good wettability between boron nitride (BN) and molten aluminum has been reported, the spontaneous infiltration of the BN powder phase with molten aluminum was investigated. The BN powder was infiltrated with molten aluminum spontaneously at 1073K. After infiltration, ceramic phases were synthesized by the reaction. By blending titanium powder with BN, aluminum nitride (AlN) and titanium boride (TiB₂) were formed by the reaction between Al, Ti and BN. However, it is crucial that the processing temperature should be higher than 1473K to achieve a complete conversion of the starting materials. Copper matrix composite reinforced by titanium boride (TiB₂) was also dealt with.

KEYWORDS: infiltration process, self-propagating high-temperature synthesis (SHS), combustion reaction, in situ reaction, heat sink, heat spreader

INTRODUCTION

A demand for producing high-performance parts or materials is getting stronger along with a development of science and technology. For example, high stiffness, good tribological performance and high wear resistance are required simultaneously for a brake disk of high speed vehicles. The higher degree of thermal conductivity and precisely-controlled thermal expansion are required in the field of semiconductor related materials such as heat sinks and heat spreaders. Hence, it turned out to be difficult to fulfil such a demand only by a monolithic material, and then technology of manufacturing ceramic/metal composites with high ceramic fraction becomes important. Technique to produce a partial reinforcement or a graded coating layer (functionally graded material: FGM) is also demanded. Ceramic components are generally fabricated by a sintering process, but high energy is required for such a process especially when high temperature materials are used. Therefore an alternative process (low energy consumption, low environmental impact and high cost performance) is called for. One of the processing methods of producing metal matrix composite is a squeeze casting. The process can be much more simplified if the infiltration takes place without applying pressure on molten metal. The reactive infiltration [1-5] aims at realizing the spontaneous infiltration with a help of either (A) good wettability or (B) heat of reaction.

(A) Infiltration by good wettability

Fig.1 shows a typical example of the reactive infiltration process with a help of good wettability. A wettable solid/liquid combination (BN_(solid powder)/Al_(liquid metal)) [1,2] is located

in a furnace. The specimen is heated and the molten metal starts to penetrate into the powder phase as the temperature increases, which is followed by the reaction shown below.

The reaction (1) can be modified as follows when titanium powder is blended with BN.

(B) Infiltration by heat of reaction

A reactive powder preform (Ti+B+Cu for example) is placed in the crucible, and then Cu ingot is located on the powder preform (**Fig.2**). As the whole specimen is heated, the reaction between Ti and B take place, which produces TiB₂ covered with Cu and releases large amount of heat. By the reaction heat, the temperature of the powder preform increases rapidly and wettability between TiB₂ and molten Cu is improved. Then the molten Cu infiltrates with the powder preform spontaneously.

Fig.1: Brief illustration of the reactive infiltration. The highly wettable combination (BN/Al) is shown as an example.

Fig.2: Brief illustration of the reactive infiltration. The reactive starting powder (Ti and B) is shown as an example.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Aluminum Composite (Infiltration by Good Wettability)

Titanium powder (<44μm) was mixed with BN powder (10μm, Ti:BN molar blended ratio = 1:2). In this paper, the blended powder of titanium and BN with a molar ratio of 1:2 is expressed as a [Ti+2BN] blended powder. The loose blended powder (3g) was located at a bottom part of an alumina (Al₂O₃) crucible, and an aluminum ingot (15g) was located on the loose blended powder as already illustrated in Fig.1. The specimen was then heated up to 1073-1673K in an induction furnace, and held for 3600s in argon gas atmosphere. After

solidification, the specimen was taken out of the crucible, and the vertical cross section was observed. A qualitative analysis was carried out by the X-ray diffraction (XRD) method.

Copper Composite (Infiltration by Heat of Reaction)

Starting materials used in this work are boron powder (<45 μ m), titanium powder (<44 μ m), copper powder (<44 μ m), TiB₂ powder (<44 μ m) and pure copper ingot. Titanium and boron powders were blended by a constant molar ratio by Ti:B = 1:2 (this powder blend will be denoted as a [Ti+2B] in this paper). Then copper and/or TiB₂ powders were added to the [Ti+2B] in order to absorb the heat of formation of TiB₂ (these powders will be denoted as 'diluent powder', meaning that the heat of TiB₂ formation is diluted by these powders). The diluent powder was blended with the [Ti+2B] by 45, 55 and 65vol%. The blending ratios of powders used in this experiment and estimated volume fraction of TiB₂ in the copper matrix after the reactive infiltration process are listed in **Table 1**. The numbers in bold and italic in Table 1 indicate the volume fraction and Cu/TiB₂ blended ratio of the diluent powder, respectively. For example, when 45vol% diluent powder is blended with the [Ti+2B] and the Cu/TiB₂ blended ratio of the diluent powder is 3/7, such a powder is denoted as a '**45(3/7)** powder'. The blended powder was compressed in a cylindrical shape (15mm in diameter, 10mm in height), and located under a copper ingot in an induction furnace. The specimen was heated at 1473K in argon gas atmosphere. The vertical cross-section was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. To understand the reaction kinetics, differential thermal analysis (DTA) was used.

Table 1 Blending ratios of powders and calculated volume fraction of TiB₂ particles

Powder	45(10/0)	45(7/3)	45(4/6)	45(1/9)	45(0/10)
V _f of TiB ₂	28	37	44	50	55
55(10/0)	55(7/3)	55(4/6)	55(1/9)	55(0/10)	65(0/10)
24	34	43	51	54	54

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Aluminum Composite

Spontaneous infiltration of molten aluminum into the [Ti+2BN] powders occurred at every processing temperatures. Microstructure of the specimen fabricated at temperatures between 1073-1673K are shown in **Fig.3**. When the specimen was fabricated below 1473K, Al₃Ti and BN were detected instead of TiB₂ and AlN. This means that the reaction (1) could not be accomplished in this temperature range. However, when the temperature was held at 1673K, Al₃Ti and BN were no longer visible.

Fig.4 shows the secondary electron image (SEI) and X-ray images of aluminum, nitrogen, titanium and boron. The X-ray images of titanium and boron overlaps where bright particles are seen in SEI. X ray image of nitrogen spreads almost over the specimen except the place where TiB₂ was confirmed. This indicate that the matrix of this composite was composed of aluminum nitride. **Fig.5** shows the XRD data of the composite fabricated at 1673K, which proves the formation of TiB₂ and AlN.

Fig.3 Effect of processing temperature on microstructure of the in situ composites.

Fig4 Secondary electron image and X ray images of the specimen fabricated from [Ti+2BN] powder

Fig.5 XRD patterns of in-situ composite fabricated at various temperatures

Copper Composite

Fig.6 shows DTA data obtained from the [Ti+2B] powder and the 45(10/0) powder. Neither endothermic nor exothermic peaks were observed from the [Ti+2B] powder within the tested temperature range (R.T.-1400K), whereas a sharp exothermic peak was observed from 45(10/0) powders at 1333K (which is close to the melting point of copper). This indicates that copper plays an important role to reduce the initiation temperature of TiB_2 formation. At around 1333K, there is an interaction between copper and titanium, which produces liquid-phase. The presence of the liquid phase is important to induce the combustion reaction, and therefore blending copper powder reduces the ignition temperature of the combustion reaction.

Fig.6 DTA data obtained from the [Ti+2B] powder and the 45(10/0) powder

Fig.7 shows the cross-sections of specimens made from 45(10/0) powders. Dark particles in the figure were identified as TiB_2 and the bright matrix was copper. The pores were hardly visible, which indicates copper previously located on the compacted powder blend infiltrated and fulfilled the pores.

Fig.7 Cross-sections of specimens made from the 45(10/0) powder (bright region: Cu, dark region: TiB_2)

Fig.8 shows the possibility of reactive infiltration of all specimens. From these results, the mapping of the possibility can be estimated. There must be a sufficient amount of [Ti+2B] powder to let the reactive infiltration occur, otherwise the heat of TiB₂ formation raises the temperature of the specimen (combustion temperature) higher than the boiling temperature of copper. This highly raised temperature causes the evaporation of copper, which causes an explosive reaction and prevents the infiltration. Even though sufficient amount of diluents is added, the Cu/TiB₂ ratio is still an important factor. When the Cu/TiB₂ ratio is low, the complete infiltration did not also occur due to the poor wettability of TiB₂ with molten copper. By controlling Cu/TiB₂ blending ratio, the volume fraction of TiB₂ in copper matrix can be varied up to 55%.

Fig.8 Possibility of reactive infiltration of all specimens and an estimated map of the possibility of infiltration

CONCLUSION

Blended powders of [Ti+2BN] were infiltrated with molten aluminum at 1073-1673K to produce ceramic/metal composites. The [Ti+2BN] blended powder was completely infiltrated by molten aluminum at every temperatures. By holding the specimens at above 1473K for certain periods of time TiB₂ and AlN were formed.

TiB₂ particle reinforced copper matrix composite can be synthesized using the reaction between titanium and boron. The heat of TiB₂ formation should be absorbed by adding Cu or TiB₂ powders. When the addition of copper or TiB₂ particles is not sufficient enough, an explosive reaction prevents the infiltration of molten copper. The blending ratio of *diluent powder* (Cu and TiB₂) is also an important parameter which determines the volume fraction of the composite and the possibility of the infiltration. Low Cu/TiB₂ blending ratio prevents the infiltration due to the poor wettability between TiB₂ and molten copper. By controlling Cu/TiB₂ blending ratio, the volume fraction of TiB₂ in copper matrix can be varied up to 55%.

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